

DMP of the project "Latvian Diaspora Identity Transformation: Text, Language, Digital Environment"

Version 1

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is developed in the framework of the Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No.5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007), grant project "Latvian Diaspora Identity Transformation: Text, Language, Digital Environment", No. BA-PA-2024/1-0019.

Funder

European Commission | EC

Grant

Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No.5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007).

Researchers

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Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: DMP of the project "Latvian Diaspora Identity Transformation: Text, Language, Digital Environment"

Description:

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is developed in the framework of the Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No.5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007), grant project "Latvian Diaspora Identity Transformation: Text, Language, Digital Environment", No. BA-PA-2024/1-0019.

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission | EC

Grants: Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No.5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007).

Project: Grant project "Latvian Diaspora Identity Transformation: Text, Language, Digital Environment", No. BA-PA-2024/1-0019.

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

Metadata for the Corpus

Metadata for the Corpus

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Collected metadata that is necessary for the corpus creation and analysis section of the project.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Other

Metadata for a corpus

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No such data currently available

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

To other Latvian diaspora literature researchers

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Excel

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-03-01

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

From the project budget

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Vita Kalnberzina (0000-0003-4755-6973)

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Some of the material that is described in the metadata is under copyright, thus the actual data gathered and shared publicly might be incomplete.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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